

Synthesis and Antiviral Activity of some Newer Formazans

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A series of 1-aryl-3-(4-hydroxy-3-methoxyphenyl)-5-(nitroaryl)formazans has been synthesised by the condensation of substituted benzoic acid hydrazides with vanillin followed by diazotisation with different primary amines. The compounds were tested for their antiviral activity against Ranikhet disease virus on chorioallantoic membrane of chick embryo but no significant antiviral activity was observed.

SEVERAL formazans were claimed to possess promising antiviral activity. For example, this class of compounds was reported active against the Ranikhet disease virus^{1,2}, and the plant viruses^{2,3}. In continuation of our studies, we report here the preparation (Scheme 1) and antiviral activity of

1-aryl-3-(4-hydroxy-3-methoxyphenyl)-5-(nitroaryl)-formazans (Table 1) expecting an increased antiviral

TABLE I—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 6-15*

Compd. no.	R ¹	M p. °C	Mol. formula
R = 3,5-Dinitro			
6	H	120	C ₂₁ H ₁₂ N ₆ O ₇
7	Cl	108	C ₂₁ H ₁₁ N ₆ O ₇ Cl
8	OCH ₃	190	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ N ₆ O ₈
9	NO ₂	110	C ₂₁ H ₁₅ N ₆ O ₈
10	CH ₃	150	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ N ₆ O ₇
R = 4-Nitro			
11	H	145	C ₂₁ H ₁₇ N ₆ O ₆
12	Cl	120	C ₂₁ H ₁₆ N ₆ O ₆ Cl
13	OCH ₃	100	C ₂₂ H ₁₈ N ₆ O ₆
14	NO ₂	95	C ₂₁ H ₁₆ N ₆ O ₇
15	CH ₃	95	C ₂₂ H ₁₈ N ₆ O ₆

Satisfactory C, H and N analyses.

activity in these compounds. However, these failed to show any significant activity when tested *in vitro* against Ranikhet disease virus (0-20%).

Experimental

Melting points are uncorrected. 3,5-Dinitrobenzoic acid hydrazide⁴ (1) and 4-nitrobenzoic acid hydrazide⁵ (2) were prepared by known procedures.

N-(4-Hydroxy-3-methoxybenzylidene)nitrobenzoic acid hydrazides (4, 5). *General method*: A mixture of the substituted benzoic acid hydrazide (0.01 mol) and vanillin (0.01 mol) was refluxed for 6 h in anhydrous pyridine (20 ml). Excess pyridine was then distilled off and the contents were poured in ice-water containing a few drops of concentrated HCl. The resulting solid was washed with water and crystallised from ethanol: 4 (R = 3,5-dinitro), 70%, m.p. 254°; 5 (R = 4-nitro), 70%, m.p. 258°; ν_{max} (KBr) 3 550 (OH), 3 325-3 320 (NH), 1 680-1 670 (C=O), 1 610-1 600 (C=N), 1 540-1 535 and 1 320-1 315 cm⁻¹ (NO₂).

1-Aryl-3-(4-hydroxy-3-methoxyphenyl)-5-(nitroaryl)formazans (6-15). *General method*: The diazonium salt solution (prepared by general procedure) was added dropwise with continuous stirring to

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a solution of *N*-(4-hydroxy-3-methoxybenzylidene)-nitrobenzoic acid hydrazides (**4** or **5**; 0.01 mol) in pyridine (20 ml) keeping the temperature below 0°. The reaction mixture was allowed to stand for about 4 h and then poured into ice-cooled water (250 ml) with continuous stirring. The resulting dark coloured solid was washed successively with cold and hot water, finally with methanol, dried in air and from ethanol (yield 70–80%): ν_{\max} (KBr) 3 550 (OH), 3 325–3 320 (NH), 1 680–1 670 (C=O), 1 615 (N=N), 1 600–1 590 (C=N), 1 540–1 535 and 1 325–1 315 cm^{-1} (NO_2); δ (CDCl_3) 3.72 (3H, s, OCH_3), 5.20–5.52 (1H, br, OH exchangeable with D_2O), 7.00–7.28 (1H, br, NH exchangeable with D_2O) and 7.30–7.80 (12H, m, ArH).

Biological activity: All compounds (**6–15**) were tested for their antiviral activity against the Ranikhet disease virus (RDV) on chorioallantoic membrane of chick embryo. The strains of the RDV was the same as employed by Babbar and Dhar⁶. Chorioallantoic membrane (CAM) of 10 days old chick embryos were taken and the culture was prepared according to the method of Babbar⁷. The results reveal that only four compounds (**8**, **10**, **11**, **14**) possessed some activity. Highest activity (20%) was shown by **14** followed by **8** (10%), **10** and **11** (5% each). All other compounds were found inactive. In general, all these compounds showed no significant activity against the virus.

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